

ISic0995

Epitaph for Tertyllanos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Cava d'Ispica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 21 cm

Width 28 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Not measured: mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Ὀπέθανεν
2. Τερτυλλαν (ὸς)
3. διάκ (ονος) κανδε
4. αύρου ἐτ (ῶν) ἀπ'

Apparatus

Text after Rizzone 2016

Translation

Commentary

The text is currently unlocated. Rizzone 2016 after Clarke 2014 demonstrates that the text comes from Cava Ispica, and not from Siracusa

Digital identifiers:

TM 492622

EDCS 39102149

PHI 140473

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0175 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9528

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.* At 2016.0621

Clarke, S. 2014. Il fascino della Cava. La storia dei Viaggiatori Inglesi a Cava Ispica. Modica. At 28

Rizzone, V.G. 2016. Una sinagoga a Cava Ispica. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik.* 200: 234-238. At 234-238

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0995. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340306>